

T2.3: Protocol for expert interviews

Author(s): Irene Monsonís-Payá (CSIC) and Richard Woolley (CSIC)

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Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	AARHUS UNIVERSITY	AU	Denmark
2.	Partner	WISSENSCHAFT IM DIALOG GGMBH	WiD	Germany
3.	Partner	NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	NTUA	Greece
4.	Partner	INSTITUTO UNIVERSITÁRIO DE LISBOA	ISCTE	Portugal
5.	Partner	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE	CNRS	France
6.	Partner	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC	Spain
7.	Associated partner	LONDON SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS AND POLITICAL SCIENCE	LSE	UK

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1 Introduction

The POIESIS project seeks to carry out a series of research activities to “systematically examine the interrelatedness of integrity, integration, and trust, and the role of institutions in fostering a research climate that is conducive to societal trust in science” (POIESIS Project Proposal, 2021:2). The project will answer its main objective through four research questions:

- RQ1: How can the nature and scale of public trust and mistrust in science be characterised and which are the factors that affect the relationship?
- RQ2: To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research *integrity* (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science?
- RQ3: To what extent and how does the *integration* of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?
- RQ4: To what extent and how can *institutions* provide policies and procedures that enable researchers to act in ways that are conducive to public trust in science?

The research plan of the POIESIS project includes a combination of analysis of primary and secondary data to respond to the different research questions and provide policy recommendations to enhance citizen trust in scientific knowledge production. Data collection includes several research activities in Work Packages 1 to 3 (Figure 1):

- In Work Package 1, secondary data on public opinion and trust is collected about the two topical areas of the project, Covid-19 and climate change. WP1 address RQ1.
- In Work Package 2 case studies are conducted to obtain primary data on the relatedness of integrity and integration and public trust with a focus on the chains of mediation between science and citizens. WP2 address RQ2 and RQ3.
- Work Package 3 examines how institutions can contribute to shaping research practices and citizen trust through a series of participatory research activities. WP3 also address RQ2 and RQ3, and RQ4.

The POIESIS project explores the role of a variety of actors who play the role of third-party mediators between researchers and publics on two topical areas: the Covid-19 pandemic and the science related to climate change. These topical focus areas were selected as both resemble each other in multiple facets, allowing comparison across cases but these two topical areas differ in other aspects, allowing for wider coverage and assessment of generalizability.

<i>Resemblances</i>	<i>Dissimilarities</i>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Both are timely and of continuous importance to a sizable set of stakeholders</i> 2. <i>They saw integrity issues emerging and entering the public debate (e.g. the hydroxychloroquine and 'climategate' cases)</i> 3. <i>The way in which data and research findings have been communicated to the public has (seemingly) had great influence on public perceptions of science for both areas.</i> 4. <i>Both are related to a wide set of academic disciplines.</i> 5. <i>Both have triggered novel discussions regarding Open Science and have, among others, led to a significant increase of data sharing, the establishment and uptake of open data and article repositories, and the use of open access publishing models.</i> 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Climate science has consistently been part of Eurobarometers and other data streams regarding public trust in science for a considerable duration, thereby providing the opportunity to trace historical trends. Pandemic related research is obviously recent, thereby allowing us to answer questions about how newly emerging themes either follow traditional patterns of mediation or create their own dynamics and chains of mediation.</i> 2. <i>Climate science has been fairly well institutionalized, among others reflected in the establishment of dedicated research centres, journals, and conferences. Again owing to its novelty, Covid-19 research is only currently going through this process of institutionalisation, thereby allowing us to study how this process affects and is affected by public trust in science.</i>

Interviews will be conducted in all POIESIS partner countries with academics and mediators with working knowledge and expertise related to either Covid-19 or climate change.

Figure 1: Data collection activities for POIESIS

This document sets out a guide for the conduct of the experts' interviews in Work Package 2 corresponding to task 2.3 of the project. The document contains the following elements:

- an overview of task 2.3 “Expert interviews”;
- a description of the study objectives and research questions
- study definitions;
- a description of the process for selecting and inviting experts;
- ethics approval;
- the expert interview instrument/guide for semi-structured interviews;
- a reporting template; and
- data processing procedures.

2 Task 2.3: Expert interviews

Task 2.3 “Expert interviews” is part of work package 2 “Small case-studies”, led by ISCTE and which main objective is “to conduct a series of small case studies based on consultative and deliberative actions to examine how practices of integrity and integration affect public trust in science with a focus on the chains of mediation between science and citizens, and to share results and recommendations” (POIESIS Project Proposal, 2021:33 Part B). In POIESIS, a chain of mediation is understood as a complex translation process. Analytically a chain of mediation can be understood as starting from knowledge production activities and the actors developing research practices on the work floor. Outputs of knowledge production can then move through a series of actors who transforming the informational form and content as it passes from one context to another.

Task 2.3 is led by CSIC and involves all project partners. The task is planned to start in August 2023 and end in February 2025 (month 12 to 30). The description of the task in the project proposal is as follow:

Box 1: Description of task 2.3 in the POIESIS proposal

Task 2.3: Expert interviews (CSIC lead, supported by all partners; M12-M30)

This task will involve interviews with mediators, academic experts, and researchers, and will be informed by the results of the public consultations. These expert interviews will be individual interviews with a sample of mediators for each topical area (16 interviews per country, 112 interviews in the consortium). This task will involve:

- Selection/Invitation of interviewees; this will be done by national teams, in collaboration with the Permanent Recruitment and Engagement Working Group.
- Preparation of the interview guide. This will be led by CSIC and the WP leader in close cooperation with all partners.
- Interviews will be conducted in each country by POIESIS partners. All interviews will be audio recorded, then transcribed and translated into English for comparative purposes.
- Analysis will include comparative elements and will focus on understanding how the chains of mediation through which responsible and irresponsible practices are conveyed may affect citizen trust in science.

The Expert Interviews will be semi-structured interviews conducted in person or online. Each interview is planned to take approximately 45 minutes. Introducing the interviews, and reciting Ethics conditions for the study before and after the interview means approximately one hour will be needed for the interaction between the interviewer and the participant. There are two groups of interviewees 'Mediators' and 'Researchers' and the interview instruments are different for each of these groups. Questions will focus on

identifying the roles and activities of the interviewee in translating scientific information to public audiences of different types. Each interview will be recorded, transcribed, and translated into English.

Preliminary categories of categorical information (e.g. job title, organisation type, etc.) that will be collected are described in the Pre-coding Scheme appendix to this Protocol. Following initial Pilot Interviews, the Pre-coding Scheme will be revisited and amended as necessary. The data collected will also take the form of descriptive passages and quotes that provide discursive responses to interview questions. Initial thematic codes will be provided in the Pre-Coding Scheme for use in analysing this discursive data. Additional codes can be created by individual coders as required and will be added to the pre-coding to form a final codebook for the interview analyses.

Each national team will write a National Report based on a template provided by the Task Leaders (CSIC). The various National Reports will be used as the basis for a comparative analysis and a summary report written by CSIC. The main output of the task, Deliverable 2.3 “Results from expert interviews” will be publicly available in August 2024.

2.1 About this protocol

As the first task of Work Package 2, the main characteristics of the process for conducting the expert interviews and the recruitment strategy were defined and included in Deliverable 2.1 "Protocol for empirical case studies" (Entradas et al., 2022).

This Protocol for Task 2.3 of POIESIS is provided by CSIC to the project partners to summarize and provide the necessary information to carry out the Expert Interviews. The document will also be submitted as part of the ethics approval process for the Expert Interviews in POIESIS, through the Ethics Committee of CSIC (the Spanish National Research Council). Updated versions of the Protocol will be provided to the Ethics body approving the study should significant modifications be required during the study process.

The Protocol (including any updated versions) will be made openly available, as with other POIESIS research protocols submitted as formal Deliverables under the POIESIS project Grant Agreement.

The document includes inputs from D2.1 and from the project meetings held by the POIESIS consortium to date. The Protocol draft will be shared among the project partners to enable discussion of its content at the Lisbon Consortium Meeting (February 2024) and subsequent revision and validation of a collectively agreed version.

2.2 Chronogram of internal activities

The completion of Task 2.3 and D2.3 requires a series of activities to be undertaken:

- Drafts of the Interview Instruments for Mediators and Researchers prepared and shared for comment with Coordinator and WP Leader

- Revision of draft based on initial comments
- Drafting of Pre-coding Scheme and Template for National Reports
- First version of the Protocol and the Interview Instruments shared with Consortium and revised following discussion at Lisbon meeting (Feb 2024)
- Piloting the interview instrument
- Revision of the Pre-coding Scheme for analysing interviews
- Revision of Template for National Reports
- Online training session for the researchers developing the interviews on the content of the protocol and instruments.
- Conduct of 16 interviews in each country
- Transcriptions and translation into English of the interviews. Writing of the national reports in English following using the template supplied (national partners).
- Writing of the comparative report resulting in D2.3 (CSIC).
- Dissemination and communication activities such as writing of a scientific paper and presenting the results at scientific conferences.

Table 1 summarizes the internal milestones of task 2.3, the projects responsible, and the expected date for completion.

Table 1: Dates and responsibilities for internal milestones in task 2.3

Month	Project Month	Milestone	Responsible
November – December (2023)	16	Draft Protocol/Guide for Expert Interviews - Materials (informed consent, information sheet, interview instrument) -Ethics approval -Joint data control agreement	CSIC
January (2024)	17	Feedback on First draft	Aarhus, ISCTE
February	18	Version 1 of Protocol and Interviews for discussion (Lisbon)	CSIC, All
March	19	Revision of Protocol & desing of National Report template	CSIC
April	20	Piloting and revision interviews	CSIC, AU
April	20	Final Protocol and Interview	CSIC
April	20	Online training for interviewers	CSIC
May - June	20-22	Interviews conducted	Each partner
July	23	National Report in English	Each partner
August	24	Synthesis Report Deliverable 2.3	CSIC
September	25	Translation of the interviews into English	Each partner
April (2025)	32	Draft scientific article	CSIC lead

3 Study objectives

The expert interviews are designed to contribute to the general objectives of WP2: examining how practices of integrity and integration affect public trust in science with a focus on the chains of mediation between science and citizens, and sharing results and recommendations.

The research questions on which work package 2 pivots are the following:

- RQ2: To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research integrity (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science?
- RQ3: To what extent and how does the *integration* of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?

In addition, the project aims to answer two research sub-questions in Work Package 2:

- How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the publics' trust in science, i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?
- What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?

The specific objective of task 2.3 Expert interviews is to understand in deeper detail the views of the 'supply' side on how (ir)responsible research practices can best be communicated and how that might affect public trust in science.

With these considerations in mind, the specific research questions for the in-depth interviews are presented in the following sub-section.

3.1 Research questions

The research questions of the expert interviews are:

- Which processes and activities connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science are identified by experts?
- How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the public's trust in science?
 - i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?

- What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?

4 Study definitions

The expert interviews seek to “study the **chains of mediation** that connect research practices at the work floor with the interpretation and assessment of these by wider publics. We will examine the **actors that play prominent roles in such chains**, to understand what their roles comprise, and how communication practices may be improved to foster public trust in science.” (POIESIS Project Proposal, 2021:8 Part B).

Figure 2: Chain of mediation: a translation process

In the context of task 2.3, a chain of mediation can be visualised as a translation process starting from knowledge production and the actors developing research practices on the work floor, moving through a series of actors (n=x) transforming that information as it passes from one context to another.

A chain of mediation can be developed in multiple ways:

- Traditional linear chain of mediation.** A chain of mediation could follow a traditional linear chain’s structure: knowledge is translated into the form of scientific dissemination practices whose results will be transformed back through institutional science communication services to reach the press and finally the public.

Figure 3: Traditional linear chain of mediation

- Traditional quasi-linear chains of mediation.** Another possibility following a quasi-linear traditional chain of mediation could be that the knowledge is transferred both from the laboratory to the publishers and to the institutional press offices, but the latter not only translates information from the laboratory but also from the publishers (Figure 4). In a similar way, the knowledge from the laboratory could be directly translated by the media (Figure 5). Thus, the translation chain incorporates complexity as multiple translations can occur among different mediators in the chain.

Figure 4: Quasi-linear traditional chain of mediation (I)

Figure 5: Quasi-linear traditional chain of mediation (II)

- Disruptive chains of mediation.** Finally, we could find chains of mediation where mediators in the traditional chains of mediators are mixed with disruptors of the chain (other content creators -such as bloggers or podders- that both create new paths and impact in the traditional model (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Disruptive chain of mediation

These models represent our initial 'ideal-type' expectations about some possible configurations of chains of mediation. Actual empirical configurations are likely to be more diverse and there are potentially a wide variety of chains of mediation linking research ethics and integrity (REI) and societal integration practices in science to the public. These models also provide an initial reference point for the possibility of asking participants in 'mediator' interviews to draw diagrammatically how they see their own position in translation and communication of science and of REI practices.

These ideal-types are simple schematics for visualising sequences of actors through which translation processes may operate. These sequences follow a simplistic linear logic that are not meant as representations of actual chains of mediation, which are likely to be far more messy and involve information flows in multiple directions. The interviews will allow participants to describe the complex information ecosystems in which they work and how they understand, interpret, and act in them. In this sense, the schematics shown are intended only as initial sense-making tools for developing a shared understanding among POIESIS interviewers.

Table 2 summarises elements that fall within our definition of chains of mediation.

Table 2: Definition of elements within chains of mediation

Element	Definition
Audience	The intended recipient of a mediating actor's output
Chains of mediation	Networks of actors, activities, and sequences of practices that connect research practices at the work floor with the interpretation and assessment of scientific research by the wider publics.
Channels	TV, newspapers, blogs, social media (Facebook, Twitter, Twitter/X, chat apps (WhatsApp/Telegram/Signal), face-to-face events/`event-makers
Intermediary	A node in the translation process that does not transform the object/output
Mediating actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional: Science communication officer working at publishers and universities • Non-institutional: Science writers, journalists and authors of science-related blogs and podcasts, and other content creators (disruptive content creators)
Mediator	A node in the translation process that contributes to transforming the object/output
Objects/outputs	Press release, Web, Blog, Article
Publics	Citizens, CSOs, social groups, clubs, etc.
R&I institutional actors	Universities, research institutes, publishers, research funders, foundations, private companies that perform R&I
Translation	Moving something from one context to another while changing it from one form to another

5 Participant selection and invitation

We will interview researchers and mediators and the selection criteria will combine a topical and process approach:

- The researchers will be topical experts in climate change and COVID-19, actively involved in studying and communicating about the content of these topical areas.
- The mediators will be professionals communicating science, but no one will be excluded by topical area. This means that mediators could be specialised in communicating climate change and COVID-19, or not. This will hence be social scientists / communication scientists and mediators reporting on a more meta-level.

Project partners will be responsible for contacting and engaging the experts, with the support of NTUA. To ensure the best selection of participants, partners will work with NTUA and the task leader (CSIC) to try and ensure the best possible approximation of the types of mediator and researcher roles foreseen in the study design. If, for practical reasons, certain criteria such as gender, cannot be met on a national level, it will be the responsibility of the task leader to ensure – at the overall project level - that this discrepancy will be compensated for in terms of the general sampling and recruitment strategy of the study. An effort will be made to recruit participants at national and project level that form a sample that is balanced in terms of gender, age, education, and social status wherever possible.

At national level the proposed selection of experts includes the following distribution of profiles (Table 3). Partners will focus on national recruitment, however, the inclusion of 'international' participants on the basis of their expertise and value-added for the project will also be possible.

Table 3: Participant profiles

Type of expert	Profile and number of experts
Researchers (6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers on climate change (3, including 1 SSH) • Researchers on COVID-19 (3, including 1 SSH)
Institutional mediators (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional science communicators working at publishers (0 or 1) – (might be allocated at the project level) • Institutional science communicators working at universities and research institutes (1 or 2)
Non-institutional mediators (8)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional science writers: authors of popular books or other content (minimum 1) • Science journalists: major print, television, radio, magazines, etc. (minimum 1) • Authors of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc. (minimum 1) • Other content creators (including disruptors, both ‘contrarian’ and ‘activist’ who use scientific research in relation to our cases) (minimum 1)

6 Ethics and research data management

This protocol and its appendices were submitted to the CSIC Ethics Committee as part of the ethics approval process for Task 2.3 of POIESIS.

As part of the study ethics approval process, project partners will be asked to sign a form confirming they have read and will comply with the Ethics requirements established in this Protocol. The compliance form is attached as APPENDIX A. Poiesis Partners ethics compliance form.

POIESIS partners in some countries may also need to notify relevant authorities of their intention to conduct research and that an ethics approval has been obtained from the CSIC Ethics Committee. It is the responsibility of POIESIS to notify the appropriate ethics institution or organisation in their countries if required.

A reference to the ethics approval information is included in the information sheet and informed consent form for participants. An informed consent must be signed by each participant. Without a signed consent form data collected cannot be used.

6.1 Ethics approval by the Ethics Committee of the CSIC

The procedure established by the Ethics Committee of the CSIC involves the following steps that were followed by INGENIO:

1. In order to initiate the ethical evaluation of the research, the investigator in charge of the research submitted the following documentation:
 - a. The Assessment Request Form, duly completed and signed, to the CSIC Ethics Committee. Research involving human subjects, samples, and/or human data (as the POIESIS project), requires filling in the data referring to the research and the researcher(s) researcher/s and answering all the questions formulated in section A of the application document.
 - b. Information sheet for participants (Appendix B)
 - c. Informed consent (Appendix C)
2. The applicant may be contacted to request further information and/or additional documentation, or to make changes to the submitted documentation.

The ethics approval application for Task 2.3 of POIESIS was submitted in December 2023. An ethics approval was received from the CSIC Ethics Committee with the approval number 300/2023 (6 February 2023). This information should be included on the information sheet and informed consented form provided to interview participants by national partners.

6.2 Data handling and management

The data resulting from the experts' interviews should be treated following the guidelines provided in the Data Management Plan of the POIESIS project (Ravn & Horbach, 2023). In this section, we will highlight the key elements of data handling and management to be considered when conducting the expert interviews.

6.2.1 Type of data collected

In Task 2.3 each national team will conduct 16 expert interviews. Therefore, general personal data (non-sensitive personal data) will be collected and stored. The identity of participants will be blinded at the earliest possible moment in the processing of the interview files. An encrypted file storing the identities of participants and linking these to the Code Identifiers (e.g. PT Cov-1, DK CC-2) will be stored securely by each national team. The precise metadata required and formatting of Code Identifiers and Interview transcript files will be specified in the National Report Template.

Signed informed consent forms will be treated confidentially by each national partner. The signed consent forms will be stored securely by each national partner in a local dedicated institutional repository.

Following the Data Management Plan of the POIESIS project (Ravn & Horbach, 2023:10), the qualitative data collected will be pseudonymised, this means that all directly identifying information from the interviews will be removed. Only national project partners collecting data through interviews will be able to reverse pseudonymisation (to identify interviewees in their national studies with the content of the interviews). Therefore, the interviewees will be preserved in all published materials from the study.

The interviews will be recorded, transcribed, and translated into English. The original recording and transcription in the original language will allow the partners to analyze the content of the interviews following a thematic analysis approach (using NVivo). The goal is to identify patterns, themes, and sub-themes that emerge from scientists' and mediators' conversations about public trust.

6.2.2 Data security: processing, sharing, and storage of data

The **original recordings and transcriptions of interviews** will be processed separately by each national project partner and safely stored through approved institutional facilities of the nationally responsible project partner. Direct quotes from the interview can be included in the descriptive-analytical summary of the interview(s). However, these should be avoided where the identity of the interviewee would be revealed. Once deliverable 2.3 has been approved, audio recordings and transcripts in the original language should be destroyed 5 years after the last publication of the expert interviews study, following the coordinator's (Aarhus University) Policy (Ravn & Horbach, 2023:19).

Prior to data collection commencing in the project, the research team will engage in a process to develop conventions for file labelling and file storage. This will be documented and will ensure coherence and shared understanding among the research team with respect to formats and standards for storing data. File labelling protocols will include Month, year and type information, along with pseudonym information for interview transcripts.

The **translated transcription** will be pseudonymised by the respective project partner and processed through qualitative analysis software (Nvivo). The translated transcription and analysis undertaken through Nvivo will be shared with the CSIC to elaborate on the final deliverable of the task. Data sharing will be done through the SharePoint used in the project POIESIS which is a secure web-based solution with Two-factor authentication (Ravn & Horbach, 2023:19). Transcriptions will be produced through Microsoft Office software (Ravn & Horbach, 2023:10). The translated transcription will be stored securely in SharePoint by the respective project partner and INGENIO, in order to analyze and describe the overall results of the Expert Interviews, which will result in Deliverable D2.3 of the project. After a period of five years after the last publication, the translated transcriptions will be destroyed.

Each partner will then produce a short report summarising the main findings. The whole corpus will then serve for comparative analysis across the involved countries, coordinated by CSIC in D2.3. The **reports** generated by each project partner will be sent by email to CSIC and uploaded to the SharePoint platform. It will be the responsibility of each project partner and the POIESIS consortium in general, to ensure that any direct quote included in the reports that is used in subsequent project outputs does not reveal the identity of the expert/interviewee concerned.

A Joint Data Control Agreement will be signed by the project partners containing comprehensive information about data security, handling, and use (APPENDIX D. Joint Data Control Agreement).

7 National reporting and coding strategy

The National Report template and codebook will be prepared by CSIC. Revision and validation of both will involve discussion and opportunity to provide comments and feedback involving all partners. The template will contain two parts: Part A reporting on the Mediator interviews; and Part B reporting on the Research interviews.

Informal support sessions will be conducted by CSIC online at the end of May to review progress in interviewing with all partners. A second informal meeting will discuss the National Report writing process and ensure a common understanding of the instructions contained in the template.

Each National Report will include:

- Introduction and participants
- Categorial data collection
- Discursive thematic data summaries
- Analytical summary
- Policy recommendations

National Reports will not require any formal comparison or synthesis of the two distinct interview series. However, the analytical summary will invite reflections on results of the Expert Interview study as a whole.

8 Quality control

A simple quality control process will be used to support POIESIS partners prepare their National Reports. The complete draft of each report will be shared with one other partner prior to the final deadline for submitting each report to the Task Lead (CSIC). Partners will be required to read the draft report and comment on its development and identify any areas for suggested changes or improvements. This process will also allow each partner to identify areas in which their own draft report might be improved. It will be the responsibility of each partner to respond to the comments received as they consider best.

APPENDIX A. Poiesis Partners ethics compliance form

Please return the signed form to:

Dr Richard Woolley
Coordinator, Task 2.3 of the POIESIS project
INGENIO (CSIC-UPV)
ricwoo@ingenio.upv.es

POIESIS Expert Interviews

Confirmation of compliance with the Study's Ethics Declaration

I, the undersigned [], hereby confirm to have received, read, and understood the ethics and data management requirements presented in the Protocol for Experts Interviews of the POIESIS project. When conducting the expert interviews' study in my role as project partner of the POIESIS project, I will diligently adhere to the principles outlined in the Protocol, particularly with regard to obtaining written informed consent of the interviewees, data protection, data management, and data handling. To this end, I confirm to have received the Protocol for the Expert Interviews, the POIESIS Data Management Plan (D5.2), the support material to obtain informed consent and information on Data Protection Compliance. In case unforeseen ethical issues arise during the study process, I will immediately inform the Study Lead and the Coordinator, and collaborate closely with them to resolve any such issue.

Place and date

Signature

Project Partner

An ethics approval for this research was received from the CSIC Ethics Committee with the approval number 300/2023 (6 February 2023).

APPENDIX B. Informed consent form

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

EXPERT INTERVIEWS STUDY (T2.3)

Project title:	Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science – POIESIS
Funding organization:	European Commission, Horizon Europe (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01)
Responsible researchers:	[Name, role of the responsible researcher]
Organization:	[Name of the organization]
Phone number:	[Phone number]
E-mail:	[Email]

I _____, with ID _____ [Replace with the relevant information for your country]:

DECLARE that I have read the Participant Information Sheet on the Expert Interviews Study, of which I have been given a copy, that I have been given sufficient time, that I have been given the opportunity to ask questions and that I have received sufficient information from the researcher, _____, who has explained to me the conditions of my participation in this research in an appropriate manner. I have also been assured of the confidential treatment of my data.

I further declare that I understand that my participation is voluntary, so I can freely withdraw from the research and revoke my consent, at any time, and for any reason.

- I GIVE my consent to participate in the proposed research.
- I DO NOT give my consent to participate in the proposed research.

I sign in duplicate and will keep a copy:

Date and signature of participant

I _____, researcher responsible for obtaining this informed consent, with ID _____ [Replace by the relevant information in your country]:

DECLARE that I have explained the characteristics and scope of the research to the participant, taking into account his/her capabilities, and I have informed him/her of the potential risks and direct benefits derived from the same.

Date and signature of the person responsible for obtaining informed consent.

An ethics approval for this research was received from the CSIC Ethics Committee with the approval number 300/2023 (6 February 2024).

APPENDIX C. Participant information sheet. Expert Interviews (T2.3)

INFORMATION SHEET FOR PARTICIPANTS

EXPERT INTERVIEWS STUDY (T2.3)

Project title:	Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science – POIESIS
Funding organization:	European Commission, Horizon Europe (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01)
Responsible researchers:	[Name, role of the responsible researcher]
Organization:	[Name of the organization]
Phone number:	[Phone number]
E-mail:	[Email]

I. Introduction

This information sheet is given to you as a participant in the Expert Interviews Study in the framework of the POIESIS project (Task 2.3). You are invited to participate in this activity voluntarily and are kindly requested to read this information sheet carefully and to ask any questions you may have. The ethical aspects of the research have been assessed and approved by the CSIC Ethics Committee.

II. General outline of the Project

The POIESIS project aims to study the relationship between trust, science, and research integrity and integration practices in a world where there is an increasing need for clear and open scientific information. We will run a series of events involving different actors including scientific experts and members of the public. One of these activities is semi-structured interviews to discuss and collect expert opinions on the role of science communication, scientific integrity, trust in science and scientific institutions, and public communication of science.

POIESIS is a consortium project. The project is coordinated by the University of Aarhus (Denmark) and involves the following partners: London School of Economics and Political Science (UK), Wissenschaft im Dialog (Germany), National Technical University of Athens (Greece), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (France), Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Portugal) and CSIC- Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spain).

POIESIS is being implemented in **Spain** under the leadership of **Richard Woolley, researcher at INGENIO (CSIC-UPV) - Institute for Innovation and Knowledge Management**.

Your participation in the study is very valuable as it will contribute to the advancement of knowledge in this field of science. Specifically, your participation will contribute to understanding how research practices are transferred to the public through different types of communication. You will be interviewed by trained researchers, who will conduct a semi-structured interview about your professional role, the procedures and sources of information you use in your work, your experience in science communication, and how you manage issues of integration and integrity.

III. Nature of your participation

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary and you may choose to participate or not.

Should you agree to participate, the interview will be audio-recorded for the exclusive use of the research team. The recordings will not be shared on any public platform. Participants may end their participation at any time during the interview. They may also request the deletion of their data by a simple request to the study coordinator in your country [Name and email of the responsible researcher]. However, pseudonymised data that has already been published cannot be deleted.

The experts who will participate in the interviews have been selected on the basis of their professional expertise and experience. Sixteen experts will be interviewed in each country, for a total of 112 interviewees.

IV. Procedures and information relating to the data obtained in the interview

You will participate in a semi-structured interview of approximately 45 minutes to one hour duration. The interviews will take place in the period May to June 2024 in the seven POIESIS partner countries.

The interview will be audio-recorded for transcription, translation into English, and analysis of the content, which will be used for research purposes only. The interview will be pseudonymised before transcription and translation. Pseudonymisation will be carried out by the project partner responsible for conducting the interviews in your country, [Name of the project partner]. Please take care not to mention any confidential or defamatory information during the interview.

Data management procedures will be in accordance with the European Union (EU) general data protection regulation (GDPR) and with the joint data management agreement (JDCA) managed by INGENIO (CSIC-UPV) as lead partner of Task 2.3, and signed by the rest of the project partners. Following these protocols, appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented in such a way as to ensure that data processing complies with the requirements of the GDPR and guarantees the protection of the data subject's rights. The data will be stored electronically for five years after publication of the research results.

We intend to share the project findings with all interview participants as soon as possible.

No significant risks associated with participation in the study are foreseen. Thus, no potentially critical ethical implications of the research results on human dignity and integrity, nor on the privacy of individuals, are foreseen. Participants are selected on the basis of their merit and professional positions and no high risks are foreseen in the selection of professional stakeholders for this particular study.

V. Funding of the research

The POIESIS project, Grant Agreement number 101057253, has been funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe programme (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01).

VI. Team responsibilities and financial compensation for participants

Your participation in this study is strictly confidential. Your personal data will always be processed by authorised personnel subject to the duty of secrecy and confidentiality. INGENIO (CSIC-UPV), as

task coordinator, ensures the use of appropriate technical, organisational and security measures to protect personal information. The entire research team is obliged to maintain the confidentiality of all personal data. Transcripts translated into English of the interviews will be processed by the lead partner of the task, in this case, INGENIO (CSIC-UPV).

One of the project partners is located in the UK, where there is an adequacy decision by the European Commission, and as such, applies protection measures and guarantees your rights in the same way as the European Union.

Your personal data will be kept for five years after the last publication related to the expert interviews, after which time it will be destroyed. The partners of the POIESIS consortium share responsibility for the processing of your personal data which are collected and processed exclusively for the purposes of the study, lawfully based on Article 6 (a) of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). All partners signed a joint Data Controllers Agreement.

The study is coordinated in [Name of your country] by the researcher [Name and email of the responsible researcher], who can be contacted to clarify doubts, share comments or exercise your rights in relation to the processing of your personal data. You can use the contact details above to request access, rectification, deletion or limitation of the processing of your personal data, data portability, or any other rights you may have.

[Name of the project partner] does not disclose or share information related to your personal data with third parties, except when legally required to do so.

Thus, in terms of data protection, we will comply with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), as well as with [Name of the national legislation in terms of data protection].

Likewise, you are informed that the [Name of the project partner] has a Data Protection Officer, who is [Name, email, contact data of the Data Protection Delegate in the project partner organization].

Participants will be reimbursed for any travel expenses arising from their participation in the interview.

VII. More information

As a participant in this study, you have the right to clarify any doubts you may have at any time and to request more detailed information about the research. To do so, you can contact the study coordinator in [Name of the country]: [Name and email of the responsible researcher].

For more information on the project, please visit the following website: www.poiesis.eu.

If all your doubts have been clarified and you have the conviction to participate in this study, you can sign the Informed Consent form.

An ethics approval for this research was received from the CSIC Ethics Committee with the approval number 300/2023 (6 February 2024).

APPENDIX D. Joint Data Control Agreement

Attached as a separate file.

APPENDIX E. Interview instrument: Mediators

Research interview instrument for mediators

A. Introduction

- Short presentation/recap of interview objectives
- Information about management of interviewee's personal data, informed consent

Format of the interview: This interview has five short sections. The first two sections (six questions) are designed to collect some basic information about your role in communicating about science. I would ask you to provide quite short, direct answers to these questions.

In the following three sections (total of nine questions) there will be opportunities for fuller responses and discussion.

If you are ready I will now start recording, and then begin the recording by asking if you agree that we record the interview.

B. Background

1. What is your occupation and/or professional role?
2. (*If applicable*) Could you also describe your employer organization and its main purposes or objectives?

C. Activities and audiences

3. What are the main activities that you carry out in your science communication work?
 - Prompt: what are the main outputs or products of your work?
4. What are the main channels through which you publish or promote your work?
5. How would you describe your target audience?
 - Prompt: Audience demographics (age, education)? A more traditional 'boomer' audience or the 'instatoktube' social media generation? Mix?
 - Prompt: What is the size/scale of this audience (e.g. viewers, followers, etc.)?
6. How do you interact with citizens (and/or target audience) as part of your work?
 - Prompt: Through events (e.g. science café, public fora, etc.) or continuous (e.g. comments section after online articles, social media etc.)
 - Prompt: Mainly face-to-face or online?

- Prompt: Do you consider your work highly interactive or more traditional broadcast/publishing in style?

Thank you for providing all this information. We will now move to some more open questions, starting with your information sources and how you use them.

D. Sources and translation

7. Could you please describe your professional network and main connections that are essential for you to do your work?

8. What are the main sources of information or inputs for your work?

- Prompt: Scientific articles? Press releases? Network contacts? Etc.
- Prompt: How do you assess the credibility of these inputs?
- Note: Please do not prompt for REI here
- Note: If interviewee mentions REI, fraud, QRPs, or other related topics, explore by asking for (a) concrete example(s) related to their assessment of credible sources

9. Can you describe your core 'creative process'? (possible triggers 'thought process' or 'workflow')

- Prompt: How do you work your 'magic'? ... turning these sources/inputs into the products of your work
- Note: If they are unsure, ask them to describe how they produced a successful or favourite piece of work
- Prompt: If necessary follow up to clarify the inputs/sources used in this example

10. What do you consider success in your work?

- Prompt: How do you assess that? (e.g. self-evaluation, metrics, reviews, etc.)

Thank you for those detailed responses, I would now like to ask you about research integrity and ethics in science.

E. Research ethics and integrity

11. What do you understand by the terms research ethics and integrity? [Hinge question that should be asked in this way whether the interviewee has mentioned REI previously or not]

- Prompt: How are REI issues important for your work?
- Prompt: Can you describe an example in the context of your work on Covid/Climate? (Explore if they have a positive and a negative example)

And finally, I would like to ask some questions about your (professional) perceptions about public trust in science.

F. Public trust in science

12. How would you describe the relationship between your work and public trust in science?

- Prompt: Do they see their work as aiming: to build public trust, to offer a critical perspective, to undermine or debunk science, to promote 'alternatives', etc.

Note: don't ask the following question (Q13) to a disruptor/contrarian interviewee, go to Q14

13. Have you ever felt that news about irresponsible or fraudulent practices in science could negatively affect public confidence in your work?

- Prompt: Do you have have any concrete experience? How did/do you deal with this?

14. From your perspective, what would improve public trust in science?

- Prompt: If possible explore for both REI- and citizen interaction-related suggestions

15. Would you recommend specific ways to improve trust in science among the younger 'social media' generation?

- Prompt: if unsur, probe for how to communicate with them, how to involve them

F. Debriefing

- Additional comments you would like to make us aware of?
- Repetition of agreements (consent etc.)

National partners are free to offer to disseminate study outputs to participants in whatever manner they prefer, provided they make arrangements that respect participants' privacy. National partners also have discretion about whether they provide a national language summary of (national or synthesis) results for participants, or simply make Deliverables (English) available.

APPENDIX F. Interview instrument: Researchers

Research interview instrument for researchers

A. Introduction

- Short presentation/recap of interview objectives
- Information about management of interviewee's personal data, informed consent

Format of the interview: This interview has four sections. The first two sections (four questions) cover your current position and your work in relation to the topic of COVID/Climate Change.

We will then move to questions about citizens connections to research, and finally to questions about public trust in science.

If you are ready I will now start recording, and then begin the recording by asking if you agree that we record the interview.

B. Background

1. What is your current position and professional role(s)?
2. Can you describe your work on the topic of COVID/Climate Change?
 - Prompt: has the public nature of debate and controversy affected your work?

Thankyou. I would like now to ask you about the communication of your work in the area of COVID/Climate Change

C. Case context

3. What are the main ways in which your work on COVID/Climate Change reaches the public?
4. Do you consider your work (or colleagues in your field) is accurately and fairly presented to the public by others (eg. Journalists, social media influencers, publishers, etc.)?
 - Prompt: Any experience of misrepresentation?
 - Prompt: Do you have any strategies to ensure appropriate coverage?

Thanks for those answers. I would like now to move to the topic of citizens' participation in science.

D. Integration of citizens across the research cycle

5. What is your opinion regarding increasing the involvement of citizens in scientific research? (If they are unsure, mention Citizen Science)
 - Prompt: what positives do you see? What negatives?
6. Are citizens involved in, or connected to, your own research?
 - Prompt: Do you organise dissemination, communication, or interactive events with citizens?
 - Prompt: At what stage(s) of the research cycle do you typically involve citizens? (Research cycle stages: Problematization; Research Design; Experiment or Fieldwork etc.; Analysis; Defining results; Dissemination and/or communication)
7. In your experience, what barriers are there to greater participation of citizens in science?
 - Prompt: Institutional or organisational barriers?
 - Prompt: Scientists skills or interest

Ok, thank you again for your responses. I would now like to move to the topic of public trust in science.

E. Public trust in science

8. In your experience, what concerns do citizens express about science?
 - Prompt: Probe for whether citizens express concerns about the conduct of science (fraud, unethical or irresponsible practices) or the outcomes of science (dangerous technologies, negative impacts, etc.)
9. In your opinion, what are the most powerful factors or forces driving citizens' concerns and public distrust of science, especially about Covid/Climate Change?
 - Prompt: Probe for conduct (REI) or context (misinformation, social media, public understanding, etc.)

Finally, taking into account citizens' concerns and the factors affecting distrust you described, I would like you to imagine that you have total freedom to introduce policies that you believe would lead to improved public trust in science

10. What would be your three most important policy priorities?
 - Prompt: if they are unsure, they can make change to how research is conducted (inc. REI), to institutions/organisations, to how science is communicated to the

public, to how citizen's are involved in science, or anything else – seemingly radical or left-field ideas should not be discouraged or excluded

F. Debriefing

- Additional comments you would like to make us aware of?
- Repetition of agreements (consent etc.)

National partners are free to offer to disseminate study outputs to participants in whatever manner they prefer, provided they make arrangements that respect participants' privacy. National partners also have discretion about whether they provide a national language summary of (national or synthesis) results for participants, or simply make Deliverables (English) available.

APPENDIX G. POIESIS data processing information sheet

Attached as separate file

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